

Zoroastrian Silk Traditions and the Socio-Cultural Heritage of the Silk Road

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Abstract

This study examines the material and intangible heritage of Iranian Zoroastrians in Khorasan and Tabaristan from the Sasanian period to the present, with a particular focus on their connection to the Silk Road. It investigates the timing and patterns of Zoroastrian migration and how they preserved Sasanian Silk Road heritage through silk production, related occupations, dialects, historical architecture, and ritual practices. The findings indicate that Zoroastrian migration from Khorasan and Tabaristan occurred at different times due to distinct historical and geographical factors; natural barriers in Tabaristan delayed migration, whereas Khorasan came under Muslim rule earlier.

The Tirgān festival, variations in the Dari Behdini dialects of Yazd and Kerman, and settlement names further aid in tracing the origins of migrant communities. The spatial relationship between bazaars and dakhmas, archaeological evidence from sites such as the Dakhma of Ray/Bibi Šahrbānū, the use of Farr by Zoroastrian silk merchants, and documented dress codes—including the Maknā headscarf worn in funerary rituals—demonstrate the integration of spiritual and commercial identities.

Addressing these challenges requires sustained ethnographic fieldwork, interdisciplinary archival analysis, systematic data extraction from oral traditions and historical and heritage narratives of minority communities, considered within national and transnational frameworks.

Keywords

Sasanian Silk Road, silk-related professions, Khorasan and Tabaristan, Yazd and Kerman, Iranian Zoroastrians.

Introduction

After the fall of the Sasanian Empire (from 224 to 651 CE), the Zoroastrians of Iran continued to adhere to their ancestral faith for several generations. However, with the rise of a new political order and increasing socio-religious pressures, this ancient community experienced significant population decline and waves of both internal and external migration. Among the regions most affected were the historical provinces of Khorasan and Tabaristan—key nodes along the Iranian segment of the Silk Road—where internal displacement of Zoroastrians was particularly marked.

This paper, by focusing on terminology specific to sericulture and silk trade, investigates where the majority of Zoroastrians from these two regions eventually resettled—most notably in the cities of Yazd and Kerman. It further explores how these communities preserved their roles as stewards of the intangible heritage of the Silk Road. In both cities, Zoroastrians not only maintained their traditional professions related to silk production, but also deeply embedded them within the rhythms of everyday life and the framework of their religious and ceremonial practices.

Despite the crucial historical role of Zoroastrians in sustaining the Silk Road's cultural and economic networks, little attention has been paid to their intangible and material heritage in existing scholarship. This study seeks to contribute to filling that gap, complementing major international initiatives such as UNESCO's project "Silk Roads Heritage Corridors in Afghanistan, Central Asia and Iran: International Dimension of the European Year of Cultural Heritage", as well as the 2022 inscription of "Sericulture and Traditional Production of Silk for Weaving" on UNESCO's Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity, with Iran as one of the key contributing nations.

In light of the ongoing decline in fluent speakers of Dari Behdini—the principal liturgical and cultural language of the Zoroastrian community—identifying and preserving Silk Road–related terminology has become ever more urgent. Moreover, Zoroastrian religious doctrines and ritual observances profoundly shape their cultural vocabulary and symbolic landscape. As such, any researcher working in this domain must possess in-depth familiarity with the theological and ceremonial systems of Iranian Zoroastrianism. Given the community’s historical tendency toward cultural seclusion and guardedness, the collection of reliable ethnographic data is best conducted by an insider or a highly trusted affiliate. Proficiency in both major Zoroastrian dialect groups is essential to building rapport with participants—revealing that the interviewer must possess a layered identity, combining linguistic, cultural, and ethnographic competencies beyond those of a conventional field researcher.

Methodology/Materials and Methods

The material culture and intangible heritage of the Zoroastrians in relation to the Silk Road—from the Sasanian period to the present—have largely remained underexplored. Despite the fact that this ethno-religious community has been a continuous bearer of the cultural heritage of the Silk Road, data collection has been challenging due to the dispersed nature of the Zoroastrian diaspora worldwide. Consequently, this heritage is gradually at risk of fading away. The information presented here has been sourced from private collections and anthropological museums, including the Zoroastrian Anthropology Museum in Kerman and the Zoroastrian History and Culture Museum in Yazd (Mārkār Museum).

Collecting culture, oral tradition and literature has been made possible through diverse methods. In addition to written sources that describe the quality, quantity, and

techniques of Zoroastrian women's silk textiles, semi-structured interviews, photographs, and documentary films found in family albums or archives—as well as in official institutions such as the Archive of the Ministry of Cultural Heritage of Iran, the National Library of Iran, the Islamic Republic of Iran Broadcasting Organisation, and UNESCO files—are among the key sources used in this research.

The methodology of this research is highly interdisciplinary. The approach is descriptive-analytical, and the nature of the research is qualitative. The collection of information from the Zoroastrian community, which includes literature, culture, and oral traditions, has been carried out through (1) library research, (2) fieldwork, and (3) the use of documentary films or images from personal or official archives.

The Silk Road

The term Silk Road was coined in the 19th century by German geographer Ferdinand von Richthofen, who highlighted the extensive ancient trade routes connecting East and West (Waugh 2007, 2). These routes, more than just conduits for luxury goods, enabled the exchange of knowledge, beliefs, technologies, and cultures across Eurasia, transforming cities into intellectual hubs. According to UNESCO, the Silk Roads, spanning over two millennia, served as a cultural corridor fostering trade, scientific advancement, and interreligious dialogue between Eastern and Western civilizations (Jing and Guo 2012, 46).

The expansion of the Silk Road in Iran coincided with the rise and consolidation of the Parthian (247 BCE–224 CE) and Kushan (ca. first century BCE to mid-third century CE) empires and paralleled the development of the Han Empire in East Asia (206 BCE–220 CE). These empires facilitated the emergence and strengthening of transregional exchange networks by establishing political and commercial infrastructures (Gasparini 2024, 181).

During the sixth to eighth centuries CE, Sasanian Persia emerged as the dominant power in West Asia, particularly in controlling the silk trade along the Silk Road (Zhao 2022, 23). By the mid-sixth century, the smuggling of white mulberry seeds into Constantinople—the capital of the Byzantine Empire—was not primarily intended to evade Chinese scrutiny, but rather to circumvent the Sasanian Empire. At the time, the Sasanians maintained a strict monopoly over the importation of foreign silk and sought to prevent any attempts to bypass their control over this lucrative trade (Coles 2022, 127).

Zoroastrianism and the Silk Road

Zoroastrianism, which originated among the Iranian peoples around 3,000 years ago, was the dominant religion in Iran before the Arab conquests of the 7th century (Foltz 2011, 73). Thus, the origins of the Zoroastrian faith predate the Silk Roads. Nevertheless, since Zoroastrianism was declared the official religion during the Sasanian Empire in Iran, this study focuses on the Zoroastrian heritage of the Silk Roads from the Sasanian Empire (224–651 CE) to the present day.

The history of Iran in relation to Zoroastrianism is divided into five stages: (1) The ancient heritage of pre-Zoroastrian Indo-Iranian religion; (2) The religion of Zoroaster himself; (3) The religion of the Achaemenid emperors, from Cyrus to the arrival of Alexander, which has the advantage of tangible, datable inscriptional evidence;¹ (4) Later Zoroastrianism, in which many believe deities and mythological elements rejected by Zoroaster were reintroduced; (5) The religion of the Magi, if it is indeed something distinct (Barr 1985, 221). Most scholars recognize the five traditional stages of Zoroastrianism throughout different periods of Iranian history. However, when examined through the lens of the Silk Road's connection with the historical phases of Zoroastrianism in Iran, along with the tradition of Zoroastrian silk weaving and their subsequent forced migration, an alternative six-stage classification emerges:

(1) the pre-Sasanian era, prior to the third century, during which there is insufficient scholarly consensus regarding the establishment of Zoroastrianism as the official state religion; (2) the Sasanian period, spanning from the third to the 7th century, characterized by the formal adoption and institutionalization of Zoroastrianism as the state religion; (3) the post-Sasanian era, coinciding with the rise of Islamic empires (7th to 9th century) and the transitional centuries known as the Iranian Intermezzo (9th to 11th century); (4) the consolidation of Islam, which led to the transformation of Zoroastrians into a marginalized minority (11th to 13th century); (5) from the 13th century until the end of the Qajar dynasty in the 20th century, during which Zoroastrians faced increasing social pressures from the majority society aimed at eroding their cultural, religious identity, and enforcing dress codes; and (6) From the 19th century to the present, coinciding with the onset of industrialization in Iran, the population of Zoroastrians has significantly declined and become dispersed worldwide. This process has not only led to the gradual disappearance and neglect of their traditional silk weaving practices but also endangered their spoken dialects.

Silk, Textiles, and Weaving in Zoroastrian Religious Literature

The Greater *Bundahishn*, also known as the Iranian *Bundahishn*,² compiled in the post-seventh century period, provides a foundational account of creation according to Zoroastrianism. This text not only dedicates various sections to different types of plant fibers, including Deccan hemp (*Hibiscus cannabinus*) and cotton as sources of fiber production, but it also explicitly references various plants that can be utilized in mat weaving. Furthermore, a distinct section is devoted to dye plants, which include saffron, indigo, dyer's madder, turmeric, logwood, and others (West 1897, chap. 9). In the description of the first human couple, Mashya and Mashyana, as shown in Figure 1, Chapters IX, Sections 101–102 of the *Bundahishn* describe a pair of plants within which

God creates the *Farr*—a divine force that exists prior to the creation of any human being and becomes attached to the body at the moment of creation. Following this, the first human couple is taught the craft of weaving (Anklesaria 1956). Also, in the Sasanian tradition, *Farr* manifests as a symbol of the king’s divine authority, which is prominently depicted in the motifs of silk textiles from this period, as shown in Figure 2. (Dode 2022, 158).

One of the tools that Zoroastrian silk merchants continue to use to this day is a torc-like ring, commonly worn as a bracelet often made of silver, known as *Farr*.

The *Farr* exists in two forms:

- (1) A bracelet featuring multiple small loops to which individual silk ribbons/tablet woven strips are attached. Each one hangs from a separate loop, collectively representing the merchant’s collection. The bracelet features a clasp mechanism that allows it to be opened and closed, enabling the addition or removal of loops as silk ribbons/ tablet woven strips are added or taken away.
- (2) A bracelet without loops, to which rectangular strips of silk fabric—displaying complete and distinct motifs—are attached. This form showcases the merchant’s collection of silk textiles. (Shahani, pers. comm., November 20, 2024)

Among the kings endowed with *Farr* is Hushang, a figure who—according to Zoroastrian tradition and its sacred texts—is recognized as the first to transmit the art of weaving, originally taught to the first human couple, Mashya and Mashyana, to the rest of humanity. He is also the first person associated with the mastery of metallurgy. It is possible that the symbolic association between the metal ring and *Farr* finds its roots in the myth of Hushang (Vevaina 2024, Dēnkard Book 9, Nasks 1–3). In addition to Hushang, two other kings mentioned in Zoroastrian literature are associated with *Farr* as well as with textile arts and fabric production. Jamshid was the first to utilize flax fibers,

silk, and natural pigments for dyeing, and he instructed people in spinning thread and sewing garments (West 1897, ch. 1; ch. 10).

Tahmuras, another king endowed with Farr, has a life story directly connected to silk. In one account, he is depicted as a figure who acquires the knowledge of silk-spinning and filament production from demonic beings (Vevaina 2024, Dēnkard Book 9, Nasks 1–3). In another narrative, his wife makes a pact with the devil, who then teaches her the art of sericulture (Pashootanizadeh 2024, 125).

Figure 1. The *Farr* of *Mashya* and *Mashyana*, illustrated within a white circle, is shown as being linked to a plant emerging from above, while the first human couple appears as two abstract, gendered beings—male and female— from whose heads a plant is growing. Note: Description by the author; image source: *Zartošti-dūzi* (silk thread embroidery), antique Zoroastrian wedding shirt embroidered with silk brocade, Safavid Dynasty, circa 1700 (1501–1722 A.D.). (*Textile as Art* 2025).

Figure 2. The symbol of *Farr* consists of a torc-like ring enclosed within a red circle, from which two silk ribbons, enclosed within a green rectangle, are shown fluttering. Note: Description by the author; Image source: first quarter of the seventh century (Dode 2022, 158).

Zoroastrianism in Iran

In the 7th century, following the Arab conquest and the fall of the Sasanian Empire, the majority of the Persian population gradually converted to Islam, leading to the marginalization of Zoroastrians as a religious minority (Foltz 2011, 73). Although Islam was established as the official religion of Iran, Zoroastrianism continued to survive in certain regions well into the late 11th century.

From the 9th to the 11th centuries, a period often referred to as the Iranian Intermezzo or the Persian Renaissance, Zoroastrian culture maintained a persistent presence across various regions of the country—from Khorasan³ and Tabaristan⁴ to parts of central Iran (Pashootanzadeh 2025, 127).

However, it is certain that Zoroastrianism gradually lost its former predominance after the fall of the Sasanian dynasty and until the Mongol conquest in the early 13th century, eventually becoming a subordinate minority religion (Stausberg, Arab, and

Maleki 2023, 826). Over the ensuing centuries, the number of Zoroastrians dwindled to fewer than 10,000 individuals. Geographically, the faith contracted from a religion characterized by diverse regional and local traditions to being largely confined to the desert cities of *Yazd* and *Kerman* and their surrounding villages (Stausberg 2002, 365).

In the 1970s, the number of Zoroastrians almost tripled, to some 25,000 adherents, and their geographical spread widened to different parts of the country; and from the 1960s onward, the greatest share of the Zoroastrian population was to be found in the capital *Tehran* (Stausberg 2002, 240). The process of increasing the Zoroastrian population in Iran stopped with the beginning of the Iranian Revolution in 1979, and Zoroastrians preferred to leave their homeland and immigrate (Stausberg 2011, 331). However, according to information provided in the Atlas of Religions, the Zoroastrian population in their homeland today is less than 20,000, and statistics published in the official Iranian government census about a decade ago indicate that Zoroastrians constitute less than 0.03 percent of the total population of Iran.⁵ It seems that the official number of Zoroastrians in Iran should be between 15,000 and 20,000 people (Rivetna 2013, 1). Some research data present figures that do not closely correspond to the actual number of adherents of Zoroastrianism. For instance, a study published in 2023 estimated the Zoroastrian population in Iran at approximately 8% of the total population, amounting to nearly four million individuals. However, this estimate reflects less the number of genuine adherents of the faith than a segment of individuals who, while expressing an inclination toward Zoroastrianism in contrast to the country's official religion, lack substantial or systematic knowledge of Zoroastrian culture, language, and religious teachings (Stausberg, Arab, and Maleki 2023, 824).

Zoroastrian Migration from Two Silk Road Centres in Iran

Following the collapse of the Sasanian Empire, two major Silk Road centres, Khorasan and Tabaristan, remained predominantly Zoroastrian and continued their involvement in the silk economy. Khorasan held a prominent position in the trade of silk textiles (Al-Maqdisi 1982, 474–475; Ibn Faqih 1988, 87), while Tabaristan, recognized as one of the main centres of sericulture, played a key role in the production and distribution of raw silk (al-Jahshiyari 1969; Bayhaqi 2004; al-Ṭabarī 2005). The accounts of Al-Ṭabarī, Al-Jahshiyari, Ibn al-Faqih, Al-Maqdisi, and Bayhaqi—all of whom lived during the 10th and 11th centuries—indicate that at least until the 11th century, Zoroastrians of Tabaristan and Khorasan remained actively engaged in silk-related professions.

All these factors, along with reports from foreign travelers up to the 19th century highlighting the high quality of silk textiles produced by Zoroastrians (Pashootanzadeh 2020, 254), demonstrate the continuity and preservation of the Silk Road's cultural heritage maintained by the Zoroastrian community in Iran.

From Tabaristan and Khorasan to Kerman and Yazd

Many historical sources have reported that *Khorasan* was swiftly occupied by the Arabs; however, *Tabaristan*, due to its challenging geography—including dense forests, marshy terrain, persistent rainfall, high humidity, and strong resistance from its inhabitants—remained beyond the reach of early Muslim conquests for a significantly longer period (Chokan, Salim, and Hasan 2023, 131). Notably, *Qutayba ibn Muslim*, who was appointed governor of *Khorasan* following the Arab conquest of Iran and rose to prominence as a capable military commander under the powerful Umayyad caliph *al-Walid I* through his successful campaigns across Transoxiana, never managed to approach *Tabaristan* (Azami Sangasari 1977, 62).

This historical evidence, along with the relative accessibility of *Khorasan* compared to the challenging terrain of *Tabaristan*, strengthen the hypothesis that Zoroastrians from *Khorasan* were compelled to migrate during the post-Sasanian era, whereas the Zoroastrians of *Tabaristan* likely migrated later, in connection with the period of the consolidation of Islam in Iran.

However, by examining the following four items, further evidence regarding the settlement of Zoroastrians in both regions can be found.

(1) Cultural Geography and Territorial Identity

Given the commercial significance of silk production along the Silk Road in *Khorasan*, and the designation of three⁶ out of nine Silk Road stations as “*Gabr-Ābād*”—meaning “Zoroastrian quarter”—in the region known as *Khorasan* within the current geographical borders of Iran, it is evident that Zoroastrians named their settlements with identifiers reflecting their territorial and communal identity.

This same pattern is traceable among the Zoroastrian community in Gujarat, India, who migrated from *Khorasan* (Hodivala 1920). They named their second settlement *Sanjān*, the oasis near *Merv*,⁷ which was the largest commercial hub for silk during the Sasanian period in *Khorasan*. Similarly, Zoroastrians who migrated from *Sari*—the principal silk production centre of *Tabaristan*—to India named their second settlement “*Navsari*”, meaning “New Sari” (Raiygani and Saadat Mehr 2021, 121). This naming practice by Zoroastrians was possible during their period of dominance as the official religion of the Sasanian Empire or at the time of their migration from Iran for naming places. However, subsequently, migrants within Iran continued to apply the same method in choosing their own names.

Considering that “*Kabul*”⁸ was regarded as part of Greater *Khorasan* during the heyday of the Silk Road, many Zoroastrians in *Kerman* adopted the surname “*Kaboli*”,⁹ derived from their ancestral homeland. A similar naming practice is observed among Zoroastrians who later migrated to India from *Kerman* or *Yazd*; they often gave their children the names “*Kermani*” or “*Yazdi*”¹⁰ to preserve the memory of their place of origin (Hormozi, pers. comm., December 9, 2024).

(2) Dari Behdini language and Silk terminology

The spoken language of Iranian Zoroastrians, known as the Dari Behdini language,¹¹ is entirely oral and divided into two distinct dialects. This linguistic division can help identify the identities of the migrant communities settled in *Kerman* and *Yazd*. Zoroastrians residing in *Kerman* speak Dari Behdini with an accent associated with northeastern Iran, commonly referred to as the *Khorasani* dialect, while those in *Yazd* use the *Perso-Tabari* dialect (Pashootanizadeh 2022).

Considering the lexical differences between the two dialects of *Dari Behdini*, the terminology related to silk and silk products used by Zoroastrians in both regions serves to identify the native origins of their inhabitants.

- The term “*Milāni*” referred to the most expensive type of silk, which was produced in *Khorasan* and, therefore, was not available in *Tabaristan*. Today, this term is still exclusively used by Zoroastrians of *Kerman* (Namiraniyan, pers. comm., November 26, 2024).
- Silk fabrics under the trade names “*Dibā*”, “*Parniyān*”, “*Tofta*”, and “*Atlas*”, all varieties of satin, were part of the terminology used by Zoroastrian merchants in the *Kerman* market. However, Zoroastrian female silk weavers in *Yazd* do not use these terms.¹²

- In the terminology of silk weaving, the term “*Zari*” is pronounced as “*Šar-vofi*” in the language of the Zoroastrians of *Yazd*. It refers to a type of brocade woven with silk produced in the *Tabaristan* region (Esfandiyari, pers. comm., November 27, 2024).
- “*Lās*” silk, the coarsest and lowest-grade type characterized by rough and streaked fibers, was native to the *Tabaristan* region. This term is exclusively used in the silk-weaving terminology of Zoroastrian women in *Yazd* (Namiraniyan, pers. comm., July 21, 2025).
- The type of silk known as “*Legi*” or “*Legee*” in the terminology of Zoroastrian silk weavers of *Yazd* refers to a variety of silk that was cultivated in *Lahijan*, a city in the *Tabaristan* region. This silk was historically transported from *Tabaristan* to “*El-Ābād*” in *Yazd*—a Zoroastrian neighborhood—during the early Islamic centuries (Pashootanzadeh 2020, 253).
- The names of certain plants that possess both medicinal properties and are utilized in textile processes share common terminology within the dialect of Zoroastrians from both regions. The plants “*Māhruvi*” and “*Tahurog*” (p. 270), both belonging to the “*Blepharis*” genus (Subramanian, Krishnasamy, Devaraj, Sethuraman, & Jayakumararaj, 2011), as well as “*Jizi*”, referring to the plant “*Tragacanth*”, are terms employed by silk weavers to denote substances used for joining broken threads during weaving. Nevertheless, the natural habitats of these plant species indicate the original provenance of this terminology among specific Zoroastrian groups. All of these plants grow in arid regions, and the desert climates of *Kerman* and *Yazd* provide favourable conditions for their growth. As a result, the related terminology has been incorporated into the lexical traditions of both ecological zones. However, their place of origin is *Khorasan*, from where, following the settlement of the Zoroastrians of *Tabaristan*—

who, prior to their familiarity with these desert plants, had used apricot gum—these terms entered the silk-weaving terminology of Zoroastrian *Yazd*.

(3) Zoroastrian Historical Structures

Although there are several recognized Zoroastrian dakhmas or “Towers of Silence” (funerary structures) in Yazd—including the dakhma of Čam village, the dakhmas of Sharifābād, the dakhma of Tarkābād (also known as the Deylam-dakhma), and the dakhma of Allāhābad-e Rostāq—none of these structures compare in architectural scale or historical significance to the ancient dakhma in Kerman (Nikzad, 2021). The presence of this funerary structure in Kerman, dating back to the Sasanian period or shortly thereafter, suggests that Zoroastrian migration to Kerman likely began during the early Islamic era (Raoufi & Khajepour, 2018), while the migration of Zoroastrians from Tabaristan to Yazd appears to have occurred somewhat later.

Additionally, the presence of the Zoroastrian *Bazaar-e Qeysarieh*, registered as a national heritage site of Iran on 14 June of June, 1987 (Registration No. 1729), and known as the largest centre for the sale of silk textiles by Zoroastrians in *Kerman* up until the Qajar period, serves as strong evidence of the continuation of the Silk Road’s cultural economy by the Zoroastrian community in *Kerman*, at least until the 18th century (Iran Shahr Architecture and Urban Planning Encyclopedia, n.d.).

Therefore, considering that the majority of the Zoroastrian community in *Khorasan* was actively involved in the silk economy, it is more likely that most *Khorasani* Zoroastrians settled in *Kerman* and continued to play a significant role in the silk textile trade, whereas the Zoroastrians of *Tabaristan* primarily settled in *Yazd*, as is further supported by the genetic proximity of the *Yazdi* Zoroastrians to the population of *Mazandaran*, the center of ancient *Tabaristan* (Grugni et al. 2012, 4).

Moreover, comparing the distance between the *dakhma* and *Bazaar-e Qeysarieh* in *Kerman* with that between the *dakhmas* and the silk textile bazaar in *Yazd* offers a meaningful insight into the nature of silk-related occupations among Zoroastrians in these two regions.

3.1. The *dakhma* and silk textile Bazaar

Classical authors such as Herodotus, Agathias, and Strabo have also provided descriptions of the Zoroastrian *dakhma* (Ahmadi & Mehrafarin 2020, 4). Moreover, many Zoroastrians religious texts such as the *Vendidad*, *Menog-i Khrad*, *Shayest Ne Shayest*, and the *Rivayats* discuss in detail the proper treatment of the body of a deceased Zoroastrian. To prevent pollution of the four sacred elements—water, air, earth, and fire—Zoroastrians were prohibited from burying the dead, cremating them, or disposing of the body in water. Instead, the corpse was placed on an elevated and remote structure to be consumed by scavenging animals and birds (Boyce 1975, 156–165, 325–330).

Nonetheless, Zoroastrians did not leave their deceased naked in the *dakhma*. *García de Silva Figueroa*, in his travelogue, notes that Zoroastrians dressed the deceased in their finest clothes when placing the body in the *dakhma* (Figueroa 1984, 206). *Adam Olearius* also mentions adorning the corpse with gold chains and jewelry (Olearius 1990, 615). Furthermore, *Jean Chardin*, while confirming *García de Silva Figueroa*'s observations, emphasizes that the body was laid upon a mattress and pillow (Chardin 1956–1966, vol. 8, 75, 99) All these historical sources indicate that the deceased was placed in the *dakhma* wearing luxurious clothing and accessories, while being laid on a bed with due respect. Therefore, it is plausible that the fabric of most of the garments was silk.

The silk textiles discovered in the *dakhma of Ray/Bibi Šahrbanū*—dating from the 7th to the 14th centuries (Moini and Rollman 2017, 10158)—along with an oral

tradition from *Khorasan* that refers to the burial of the daughter of the last Sasanian king, reportedly dressed in silk garments at this very site (Pashootanzadeh 2025, 246, 258), reinforce the likelihood that the clothing of the deceased was made of silk.

The location of this *dakhma* in the city of *Ray*—situated precisely along the main trade route for transporting silk textiles from *Tabaristan* to *Khorasan* (Hassannejad and Khalife 2012, 49; Vedeler 2014, 91)—suggests that silk fabrics were abundantly available for dressing the deceased. Furthermore, prior to the destruction of Zoroastrian *dakhmas*,¹³ Zoroastrian women were traditionally laid to rest wearing their long silk headscarves, known within the Zoroastrian community as “*Maknā*”.

The *Maknā* functions as a form of social skin in Zoroastrian women's rites of passage, symbolizing the transition between key stages of life—such as from virginity to marriage or from life to death—much like other ritual head coverings across cultures (Kim 2025, 213). The colour of the *Maknā* in Zoroastrian women's attire functioned as a dress code indicating their marital status. Upon death, they were placed in the *dakhma* wearing a *Maknā* of the same colour. This final *Maknā* was traditionally prepared and presented by the husband—provided he was still alive¹⁴—for his wife to wear.

In traditional Zoroastrian marriage customs, each of the five types of marriage—practiced since the Sasanian era (Salehi and Naderi 2014, 93) and continuing until approximately a century ago—was associated with a specific colour of the silk *Maknā* worn by women as part of a codified dress code. The *Maknā* for *Pātaxšāyih* marriages was green (*Sāvz* in the *Dari Behdini* language); for *Ayōk-zan*, yellow (*Zārd*); for *Satar(o)r-zan*, red (*Sowr*); for *Čākar-zan*, blue (*Owvi*); and for *Rāy-zan*, purple (*Benāfš*). Additionally, the colour orange (*Nowrenji*) was designated for unmarried girls, symbolizing their transitional social status before marriage.

Given the emphasis on the concept of purity in Zoroastrian religious beliefs (Pashootanzadeh 2025, 136), it was preferred that the deceased be dressed in a new *Maknā*. Consequently, the proximity of the *dakhma* to the textile bazaar became both a ritual and practical necessity. Zoroastrian women in *Yazd*, most of whom were engaged in silk weaving, either produced textiles on commission for silk merchants or sold their own woven fabrics directly in the fabric Bazaar.

As a result, the *Yazd* cloth bazaar was located close to the Zoroastrian *dakhma*—approximately eight km away—to facilitate access to silk cloth for funerary purposes.

Although the Zoroastrians of *Kerman* also adhered to this tradition and required silk fabric for their deceased, they did not need to visit the *Bazaar-e Qeysarieh*. This was because most Zoroastrians in *Kerman* were silk merchants who resided within the Zoroastrian neighborhood and stored their silk textiles in home-based warehouses for enhanced security.

Instead, the Zoroastrian merchants used their *Farr*—a collection of silk productions—to present their inventory to retailers. When an agreement was reached, the ordered quantity of silk was dispatched directly from the merchants' home warehouses to the retailers. Given these logistical arrangements, it is not surprising that the distance between the Zoroastrian *dakhma* in *Kerman* and the *Bazaar-e Qeysarieh* spans approximately 210 km.

(4) The Tirgān Festival¹⁵ and Tir

Tirgān is a Zoroastrian religious festival associated with the longest day of the year. It is held in the month of “Tir” in the Iranian/Zoroastrian calendar, which corresponds to the first day of July. Tirgān is held in honor of Tishtrya, the Zoroastrian divinity of rain (*Zoroastrian Calendar of Iran* 2025). This celebration holds particular cultural and

historical significance in the regions of Tabaristan and Khorasan, which evoke the legacy of the Silk Road. This connection has contributed to the continued observance of the festival in these areas up to the present day.

In Zoroastrian religious literature, the heroic figure *Ārash* is celebrated for shooting an arrow—pronounced *Tir* in Persian—from *Tabaristan* toward *Khorasan*, thereby marking the borders of Iran. The festival commemorates this legendary act (Ibn Isfandiyar 1987, 86). The repetition of the term *Tir* as both the name of the month and the arrow holds significance in relation to the terminology and the distinctive styles of silk productions among the Zoroastrians of *Yazd* and *Kerman*.

Zoroastrian women silk weavers in *Yazd* craft colourful bracelets from silk threads—known as “*Tir o Bād*”—to give as gifts during the *Tirgān* festival and the word *Tir* simultaneously refers to both the arrow and the name of a month in the Zoroastrian calendar, while *Bād* denotes a gentle breeze or wind, believing that wishes reside within them, much like silkworms within their cocoons (Pashootanizadeh 2020, 256). After ten days, these wishes are thought to transform into butterflies and take flight with the wind. On the day devoted to the deity of wind, the bracelets are released into the breeze in hopes that the wishes will be carried away and fulfilled (Pashootanizadeh 2024, 126). This custom was not originally practiced in *Kerman* but is considered an imported tradition, likely due to the city’s longstanding history in the silk trade, whereas sericulture, silk weaving, and the production of silk tablet-woven strips are indigenous to *Yazd*.

The earliest example of Iranian patchwork using factory-produced cotton fabrics was created by Zoroastrian women in *Yazd* during the Qajar period (Salehieh Yazdi and Saber 2022, 109). This particular form of patchwork emerged as a creative response to discriminatory regulations of the Qajar era, which prohibited Zoroastrians from purchasing imported cotton fabrics. Muslim fabric merchants who did not employ the

symbolic display tool known as *Farr* would arrange rectangular strips cut from fabric bolts on a table in front of their shops to serve as a makeshift showcase. The main stock of fabric was stored inside the shop, and customers, after selecting the desired type of textile from these display strips, would present them to the merchant in order to purchase the required length. After a particular fabric was sold out, the rectangular display strip was discarded. Zoroastrian women of *Yazd* would collect these discarded fabric strips and create patchworks known as “*Tir o Six*” adorned with the distinctive and delicate embroidery with silk threads typical of Zoroastrian artisans—known as “*Zartošti-dūzi*” (Pashootanzadeh 2021, 124).

The silk variant of the Zoroastrian patchwork of *Yazd Tir o Six*, which is not decorated using *Zartošti-dūzi* embroidery, is known in the *Dari Behdini* language as “*Tir Tirak*” and is originally attributed to the Zoroastrians of *Kerman*. The Zoroastrian women of *Kerman* employed a method similar to that of *Yazdi* women in crafting this type of patchwork, with the distinction that they purchased silk scraps, which were hung on the *Farr* of Zoroastrian silk merchants and no longer considered part of the merchants’ collection, at a lower price (Varj, pers. comm., January 7, 2025, Michigan).

Two Zoroastrian cultural materials related to silk, namely *Tir o Bād* and *Tir Tirak*, each originate from one of the cities to which many Zoroastrian migrants from *Tabaristan* and *Khorasan* relocated. These Zoroastrians, who were engaged in silk-related professions, created distinct examples of silk cultural productions according to their occupational connections.

Conclusion

This study reveals that Zoroastrians from the regions of *Tabaristan* and *Khorasan* migrated at different times due to distinct historical and geographical factors. The natural barriers of *Tabaristan* hindered Muslim rulers’ access, delaying migration, whereas

Khorasan was conquered earlier by Muslim forces. This temporal difference is supported by the relative dating of the *dakhmas* (Zoroastrian funerary towers) in *Kerman* compared to those in *Yazd*, suggesting that Zoroastrians from *Khorasan* migrated earlier. Moreover, the *Khorasani* Zoroastrians' occupations, closely linked to Silk Road merchants, led to the establishment of specialized silk bazaars in *Kerman*, notably the *Bazaar-e Qeysarieh*, which remained a symbol of continuous silk trade by Zoroastrian merchants at least until the 20th century.

The spatial relationship between the silk textile bazaars and the Zoroastrian *dakhmas* (funerary towers) plays a significant role in identifying occupations related to silk among Iranian Zoroastrians. Historical travel accounts and documented dress codes confirm that Zoroastrian burial customs involved silk garments, including *Maknā*, the ceremonial headscarf traditionally worn by Zoroastrian women during transitional life stages such as marriage and death. Moreover, archaeological discoveries from the *Dakhma of Ray/Bibi Šahrbanū*—situated along the historical corridor linking *Tabaristan* and *Khorasan*—reveal silk textiles dating from the 7th to the 14th centuries, further evidencing the ritual and symbolic role of silk in Zoroastrian culture. The *Farr*, a distinctive emblem rooted in Zoroastrian religious ideology, was used exclusively by Zoroastrian silk merchants, reflecting the integration of spiritual and commercial identity. The continued celebration of *Tirgān*—a national and religious Zoroastrian festival—in regions such as *Tabaristan* and *Khorasan*, and its local adaptations in *Yazd* and *Kerman*, demonstrate how regional engagements with the Silk Road and related occupations gave rise to diverse material legacies within Zoroastrian communities.

Linguistically, the *Dari Behdini* dialect differs between *Yazd* and *Kerman*: inhabitants of *Khorasan* spoke the *Khorasani* dialect, while those from *Tabaristan* used

the *Perso-Tabari* dialect. The names of Zoroastrian settlements and the importance of territorial identity have assisted in tracing the original homelands of these migrants.

Overall, the Zoroastrian community, as both a religious and ethnic group, has been instrumental not only in preserving silk-related traditions but also in safeguarding the tangible and intangible heritage of the Silk Road, deeply intertwined with their religious beliefs. However, population decline, the increasing transformation of Zoroastrian communities into a global diaspora, and the erosion of traditional languages and occupational knowledge place this heritage at considerable risk. Addressing this vulnerability calls for sustained ethnographic engagement, interdisciplinary archival research, and a more inclusive approach to heritage governance that foregrounds minority narratives within national and transnational heritage frameworks.

Preserving Zoroastrian silk-related heritage is therefore not only a scholarly endeavor but also a social and ethical imperative. Recognizing and safeguarding this legacy contributes to a more inclusive understanding of Silk Road heritage and affirms the enduring cultural contributions of one of the world's oldest living religious communities.

Notes

¹ Limited but credible evidence has been obtained in archaeological research that identifies the Achaemenids and the Parthians as followers of Zoroaster (Boyce 1996, 13). Archaeological evidence from the Nisa ostraca and the Parthian parchment from Avroman, found in various parts of the Iranian plateau, proves that the Parthians used a Zoroastrian calendar that is similar to the current Zoroastrian calendar (de Jong 2008, 24). Although the Sogdians, who had temples during the Tang dynasty in China, considered themselves Zoroastrian, they did not implement Zoroastrianism as a state-organised religion like their western neighbours (Lerner 2001, 226–27).

² There are two versions of the *Bundahishn*: one known as the Iranian *Bundahishn* and the other as the Indian *Bundahishn*.

³ Historically, the region of Khorasan encompassed northeastern Iran, parts of Afghanistan, and southern Central Asia up to the Amu Darya (Oxus) River. In broader usage, the term has also referred to a wider area that included much of Transoxiana, including present-day Bukhara and Samarqand (Minorsky 1938, 621–652).

⁴ Tabaristan, until the 13th century, encompassed parts of present-day Mazandaran and Gilan provinces, covering the southern coastal regions of the Caspian Sea up to the Alborz Mountain range (Ibn Isfandiyar 1987).

⁵ After the COVID-19 pandemic (2019), due to the aging population of Zoroastrians, the number significantly decreased compared to 2012.

⁶ *Gabr-Ābād* was the historical name of *Birjand*, *Qarehcheh* village, and the original local name of *Eslamabad*, all located in the Khorasan region.

⁷ According to Pargari, Merv was recognized as the largest centre for the sale of silk textiles even up until the 9th century (Pargari 1997, 49).

⁸ Ibn Khordadbeh and the *Hudud al-'Alam* refer to Kabul as part of the Khorasan marches, a frontier region situated between Khorasan and India (Minorsky 1937).

⁹ “*Kaboli*” means someone who comes from *Kabul*. “*Iraj Kaboli*” is one such example. See Wikipedia contributors, “*Iraj Kaboli*”, *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, accessed August 3, 2025, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Iraj_Kaboli.

¹⁰ “*Yazdi*” means someone who comes from Yazd. “*Yazdi Karanjia*” is one such example. See Wikipedia contributors, “*Yazdi Karanjia*”, *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, accessed August 3, 2025, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yazdi_Karanjia.

¹¹ The language of the Zoroastrians has two main branches (Kermani and Yazdi) and more than twenty sub-branches, which correspond to the diversity of their habitats (Pashootanzadeh & Sharifiyan 2020 and Gholami 2018, 209).

¹² Zoroastrian silk weavers of Yazd use the term “*Dori*” for “*Dibā*”, “*Viporz*” for “*Parniyān*”, and “*Belaxš*” for “*Atlas*”.

¹³ Due to the use of Diclofenac, which entered the scavenger food chain through human corpses and led to the death of vultures, the use of dakhmas was prohibited in order to prevent the extinction of these birds (Enayatizadeh and Amouzegar 2018, 103).

¹⁴ In the past, many women died at a young age, often during childbirth.

¹⁵ registered as Iran’s intangible cultural heritage in 2011, No. 192.

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